

Success Factors Consideration for E-banking Web site from User Perspectives in Malaysia: A Study Using the Knowledge Transfer Process Model

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Abstract

E-banking is a self-service technology and recognized as one of the components of current economic growth, and a strong value-added tool to encourage new customers and retain existing banking web site users. Internet users have increased dramatically, but the Malaysian Communication and Multimedia Commission Internet User Survey 2018 stated that 46% of adult Internet users do not use online services when making banking transactions. This research has adapted Szulanski's widely accepted and recognized knowledge transfer model as a lens to study the success factors which deter customers from using bank web sites. The model consists of four stages: initiation, implementation, ramp-up, and integration. This research aims to identify the success factors which affect the knowledge transfer process via e-banking web sites among banking web sites users within public universities in Malaysia. Primary unit of data collection is respondents from eight public universities in Malaysia through a structured questionnaire. Interviews were conducted with banking executives and academic experts. Pilot study conducted to indicate the instrument quality, consistency and validity, confirms the idea being measured Cronbach's alpha is more than 0.07. Statistical analysis and descriptive statistics will be used to explain demographic profiles and bank web sites user's experiences, EFA, CFA and SEM will be used to identify trends in internet bank web site usage affecting knowledge transfer process in e-banking web sites. This study contributes to the understanding of user experience and can shape perceptions of the success of factors affecting knowledge transfer process via banking web sites, extending the area of application of the four stages of knowledge transfer process in e-banking context. This provides a potential guide for developers involved in constructing web sites, particularly e-bank web sites, with insights that can contribute to making a web site a successful channel for the delivery of bank knowledge resources to users via web sites.

Keywords: E-banking, Website, Transfer Process Model

1. Introduction

Electronic services research which has become a global concern, in addition, maximizing usage of emerging technologies to support decisive business competence of future decades was addressed. E-banking web site service is hugely important because reducing time, cost and effort. E-banking is described as the utilisation of the Internet, especially via web site, to conduct all possible

financial transactions (Ilyas et al. 2013). Bank web sites are the endorsed channels for customers pursuing to connect with services and information, principally in knowledge-based web sites.

Currently, in an age whereby knowledge is an elemental asset, knowledge surges have been displayed as the fundamental influences of the global economy (Vaca et al. 2018). Therefore, by accepting knowledge as a vital for organisations and the implications on the organisation's

effectiveness and cohesion within resourceful parameters, an urgent need has arisen to construct techniques for establishing, transferring and engaging knowledge within firms. In pursuance of utilising this invaluable resource, organisations should manage their knowledge soundly (Dayan et al., 2017). Knowledge plays a fundamental aspect for the banks and the capacity to compete profitably on financial markets. At the initial position, banks have considerable advantages due to their information and services regarding domestic markets and customer requirements. Knowledge transfer (KT) is an interactive process involving the interchange of knowledge between service providers and service users. Several researchers have looked into KT, as per its benefits to understand customer needs, preferences and attain organization competitive performance in different context (Azizan et al., 2011; Giannakopoulos et al. 2013; Farzin et al. 2014; Nakanishi 2014; Aghdasi et al., 2015; Torabi et al., 2016) but there is a lack of studies of success factors for KT via banking web sites. Success factors are set of factors in which if they are satisfactory, will ensure successful performance (Usman 2018). This paper for identifying success factors will conduct literature review and their attributes for KM, KT, web-based self-service (WBSS) and e-banking.

As users play an interactive role, banking has established a user-based strategy, utilising users as the main source of knowledge in the investigation of new opportunities, because the immediate understanding of user needs affects the maximisation of new products and development of new services (Kulkarni and Kulkarni 2013).

1.1 E-banking

Banks have been investing substantially in modernising their infrastructure and applying new technologies as well as focusing on delivering services via web sites (Randiwela 2018) but still realise that using e-banking does not match provider expectations, and high numbers of clients are conducting financial transactions at the counter. Malaysian Communication and Multimedia Commission stated that 46% of adult Internet users do not use online when making financial transaction (Internet User Survey 2018).

Decision makers in the banking industry have insufficient comprehension of the needs and preferences of users who use e-banking web sites (Lumbera et al., 2019). Furthermore, the Malaysian banking sector still requires many research work to develop and enhance appropriate e-banking web site strategies in order to provide a successful

channel for providing information and services via e-bank web site (Mahmadi & Zaaba, 2018).

2. Theoretical Concepts and Definitions

The concepts success factors, 'knowledge' and 'knowledge transfer' are presented in this section. The aim is to provide a basis for discussion of knowledge and success factors later in upcoming sections.

2.1 Knowledge

The knowledge nature complexity has been discussed comprehensively in information technology (IT). Nonaka (1994) believed that knowledge should be split into tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge, tacit is personal, hard to formalize and not easily expressible, and includes beliefs and perspectives, whereas explicit is formal, systematic, easily communicated and shared, which includes manuals or reports. More specifically, what is transferred in this context is bank knowledge resources (information and services) conveyed to and engaged by users through bank web sites, which becomes meaningful to web site users only when they have interpreted and applied it in perspective.

2.2 Knowledge Transfer

Knowledge transfer has received the attention of many scholars and practitioners (Szulanski, 2000 Budiardjo and Budiardjo 2017; Liang and Wu 2010)(Aghdasi et al. 2015; binti Mohamad Sani and binti Arshad 2014; Budiardjo and Budiardjo 2017; Cader et al. 2013; Farzin et al. 2014; Liang and Wu 2010; Noor and Salim 2011; Paramsothy, Woods, and Raman 2013; Vaca et al. 2018) and point out the importance of KT in e-services in today's global market place and how it can be beneficially integrated. Since e-banking is a form of e-services, KT can assist e-banking to accomplish an ambitious edge. Paulin and Suneson (2012) defined KT as interchange of knowledge between individuals and organization whether intended or unintended, KT is an Interactions process. Banking sector still requires much research work to develop and enhance appropriate e-banking web site strategies in order to provide a successful channel for providing information and services via e-bank web site (Mahmadi & Zaaba, 2018).

KT can understand user needs and preferences by adapting the aspect of user context in forming opinions of the criticality of factors. Involving banking web sites users from different backgrounds of respondents, and based on bank web site user

experience; this aspect can construct a reinforced understanding of how user's context can form concepts of the criticality of factors. Additionally, this idea can presents more comprehensions for service providers to understand their client needs and preferences which may increase demand for e-banking web sites and user's decision to increase utilisation of e-banking web site services.

2.3 Success factors consideration

For banking organizations to leverage their knowledge potential wholly, they must first appreciate and determine the enablers that affect the entire KT process. Therefore, it is anticipated that this paper will eventually facilitate and assist the banking sector to recognize and comprehend users' needs and preferences and the affecting factors that further induce KT between the banks and their customers.

It is remarkable that the success factors are set of factors if they are satisfactory, will ensure successful competitive performance for the organisation. Therefore, banking decision makers can then administer continual and careful attention on these pivotal factors of their organisation (Cooper et al., 2009; Aquilani et al., 2017). In this paper the potential success factors for banking websites extracted from previous literature in related research area in e-banking, KT, customer services, and web-based self-service, and constructs the grouping as follow (web site user and content.

2.4 Intra-organizational Szulanski's KT Model

Currently, this paper looking to view the success factors through the lens of KT. The primary Szulanski's KT model was used to describe intra-organization KT (Szulanski, 2000). Szulanski's KT model has been selected because it is globally recognised, underpinned various studies, and tested (Cooper et al., 2007; Azizan et al., 2011; Frank & Ribeiro, 2014; Pak et al., 2015). Therefore, this paper extends Szulanski's KT model to evaluate success factors in external KT in an e-banking context.

Szulanski's KT model consists of four stages, namely initiation, implementation, ramp-up and integration. The initiation stage begins when the web site user has recognized a need for knowledge (information and services) and starts a search for knowledge to fulfil that need, consisting of all events that lead to the decision to transfer the knowledge. Once the need for that knowledge is specified, the possibility of transferring that knowledge is explored. The implementation stage begins when knowledge resources flow between the source and the recipient. The implementation related activities conclude after the recipient begins using the transferred knowledge. The ramp-up stage begins when the recipient starts using the received knowledge. During this stage, the recipient will be concerned with identifying and resolving unexpected problems that arise while using the new knowledge. Finally, the integration stage begins after the recipient achieves satisfactory results with the transferred knowledge. The use of the transferred knowledge becomes routinized. Integration is complete when old knowledge is replaced by new knowledge (Szulanski, 2000; Azizan et al., 2011).

2.5 Success Factors for KT via E-banking Web Sites

As stated above, what appears on the bank web sites are knowledge resources (information and services) administered to users (citizens and commercial bodies). Web site platforms can enhance by KT by diminishing temporal and spatial barriers between customers and banks, and improving access to banking knowledge (information and services) for customers (Meier, 2008). The banks use knowledge to underpin the users of its day to day activities and arrange planning to make the information available to the users. Banks rely on a variety of IT means for distributing collecting and storing information to their users. By using web sites to transfer knowledge resources can decrease service processing expenditure and enhance e-bank delivery (Gooraki & Shirazi, 2014). Table 1 shows the importance of success factors in KT processes in e-banking web sites.

Table 1: success factors in KT process via E-banking Web Sites

Description		Author
Bank Web site user		
Security	Bank web user needs and prefer from banks web sites to be safe, confident and has clear security policies by banks before conducting the financial transaction, during conducting financial transaction, when he face unexpected problem. Finally, after finish financial transaction he wants to be satisfied and reuse the services again.	Tan et al., 2016 Considine & Cormican, 2016
Privacy	Bank web user needs and prefer from banks to do not misuse his sensitive personal information before, during and after finish the financial transaction.	Rahi et al. (2017)
Customer support	Bank web user needs and prefer from banks to follow up user's request, keep promise with user's issue before conducting the financial transaction, during, when he face unexpected problem and after finish financial transaction.	Abdullah et al., 2015 Zhou et al., 2018
Content		
Accurate knowledge content	Bank web user needs and prefer from banks to make sure the content of web accurate and clear in meaning before conducting the financial transaction, during, when he face unexpected problem and after finish financial transaction.	Dickinger & Stangl, 2013 Sun et al., 2015
Appropriate knowledge presentation	Bank web user needs and prefer from banks to make sure the content of web free of ambiguous language, continually updated before conducting the financial transaction, during, when he face unexpected problem and after finish financial transaction.	Yang et al., 2010 Jovovic et al., 2016).
Web design layout	Bank web user needs and prefer from banks to make sure the web present attractive layout, readable font and high quality colors before conducting the financial transaction, during, when he face unexpected problem and after finish financial transaction.	Cebi, 2013 Rodrigues et al., 2017

Regarding the web site user characteristics, are considered the most dominating factors in previous research. Security is the most important factor in determining customers' overall service quality perceptions (Tan et al., 2016; Considine & Cormican, 2016). It is essential for the banks to understand the specific needs of customers and keenness of their privacy (Cooper, 2009; Brar et al., 2015). In e-services, privacy warrants a high level of concern due to gaining of personal information by a third party which can harm the consumer (Rahi et al. (2017)). Customer support in e-service contexts can affect delivery of products, customers' satisfaction, experience, intentions, or purchase decisions (Abdullah et al., 2015; Ghasemaghaei & Hassanein, 2016; Zhou et al., 2018).

Regarding content, factors that might be expected relate to understanding and having the capability to deliver accurate, required knowledge content, appropriate knowledge presentation, and web design layout. Accurate knowledge content is key stone in banking context, and is regarding the accurate content on the web site, which is clear in meaning, easy to understand, and understandable for customer to use (Dickinger & Stangl, 2013 Sun et al., 2015). Appropriate knowledge presentation one of the significant factors in knowledge-based web sites, and is regarding bank web site content that is free of ambiguous language, continually updated, simple for users, and has minimal

download time (Yang et al., 2010; Jovovic et al., 2016). Web design as a determinant to change bank clients' attitudes or behaviour to use e-banking Web design layout is related to presenting a web site in high-quality colours, presentable readable fonts, and attractive design screen layout (Cebi, 2013; Rodrigues et al., 2017).

Based on all characteristics of web site user and content above, this leads to the following hypothesis:

H1. There is a positive relationship between security and stages of KT process with respect to the use/usage of e-banking web site.

H2. There is a positive relationship between privacy and stages of KT process with respect to the use/usage of e-banking web site.

H3. There is a positive relationship customer support and stages of KT process with respect to the use/usage of e-banking web site.

H4. There is a positive relationship between accurate knowledge content and stages of knowledge transfer process with respect to the use/usage of e-banking web site.

H5. There is a positive relationship between appropriate knowledge presentation and stages of knowledge transfer process with respect to the use/usage of e-banking web site.

H6. There is a positive relationship between web design layout and stages of knowledge transfer process with respect to the use/usage of e-banking web site.

The conceptual model is illustrated in Figure 1, the independent variable are the proposed potential

success factors while the dependent variable is KT processes.

Figure 1: Conceptual model for the influence of potential success factors on KT processes via e-banking web site. Source: Own elaboration

3. Methodology

The present study aims to identify the success factors for KT from e-banking web sites user perspectives in public universities in Malaysia context. The research will commence by developing an exploratory pilot study. Thereafter,

the research design will secondly quantitative method will be used through a questionnaire survey, and thirdly through interviews with banking executives and academic experts to validate the research results. Figure 2 illustrates the research design.

Figure 2: Current Research Design

Quantitative research involves the collection of data sources such as surveys or laboratory-based experimental research data (Myers & Avison, 2011; Creswell, 2012) which is then analysed and represented in forms such as mathematical models, statistical tables and graphs (Neuman, 2005).

Quantitative research tests theories deductively, builds in protections against bias, and controls for alternative explanations and enables generalisation and replication of the findings (Creswell, 2012). In the proposed research, survey data will enable to find out the causal relationships between research

variables. Thus, the planned survey will help to uncover the relationships among success factors and the stages of KT processes via e-banking web sites from user perspectives which match definition and proposed conceptual model. Whereas the quantitative approach allow to validate and confirm the research result by banking executives and academic expert with a high level of confidence (Zikmund et al., 2010). On this basis, the researcher has ample rationale to adopt the quantitative approach in this research.

3.1 Unit of analysis

The unit of analysis is the body or individual that is being critiqued in a research. Therefore, in order to reply to the research question, determining the unit of analysis is paramount. Consistent with this aim, the population under study were e-banking users in different public universities in Malaysia such as UM in Kuala Lumpur, UITM Shah Alam, UTEM Melaka, USM Penang, UTM Johor Bahru, UniMAP Perlis, UKM Selangor and USIM Negri Sembilan who uses e-banking web sites serves as the unit of analysis in this study. This is because it is predictable that the population of this study should have information about e-banking due to their high level of education, more access and the use of communications media and internet. The population consists of people with different ages and experience, so to incorporate a variety of ages and experience groups, they comprise of different cities with different cultural backgrounds, so it is not limited to a specific city or culture. Therefore, it can be said that the population is, to a great extent, representative of Malaysian citizens, e-banking users can therefore be considered as a range of innovators in the society and this is a worthwhile reason for them using e-banking

services. Therefore, the opinions of e-banking users of public universities in Malaysia were sought regarding online banking services in the country.

3.2 Design of Questionnaire

The questions utilized in the survey were constructed and adapted from the literature review. The questionnaire divided into four parts. The cover page showed the title of the study, college, the name of University Sians Islam Malaysia, and aim of the questionnaire. Then, questions in Part 2, general information, include biographical questions. Part 3 questions pertain to the KT process including the initiation stage in KT process, and refer to the initiate stage definition in KT Model that interprets customers' need for knowledge (information and services) by using e-banking web site. Questions were also included to demonstrate the implementation stage that explains the knowledge flow between users and e-banking web sites. Questions were added to show the ramp-up stage that explains how users may face unexpected problems and resolve these problems while conducting transactions via e-banking web sites. Questions to demonstrate the integration stage were also done to show whether the clients attain satisfaction owing to transferred knowledge.

3.3 Variable Measurement

The survey comprised of 40 items except the demographic elements. Table 2 and Table 3 below summarize the instrument used for all variables. The two tables show the items used along with a summary of the measurements of previous studies related to each variable discussed in literature review chapter.

Table2: Construct Items Regarding Stages of KT Process.

Variable	Code	Adapted Statement	Source
Initiation stage	INIT 1	I need the necessary services that are offered by banking web site.	Szulanski (1996; 2000)
	INIT 1	I am not keen to share personal information with banking web site.	
	INIT 3	The interaction with banking web site is simple.	
	INIT 4	Internet banking web site is easy to use to obtain information.	
Implementation stage	IMP 1	I must have experience to use banking web site.	
	IMP 2	Using banking web site requires training.	
	IMP 3	The function of banking web site is carefully planned.	
	IMP 4	I am using banking web site based on expert recommendation.	
Ramp-Up stage	RMP1	I am afraid of using internet banking services because I may face an unexpected problem.	
	RMP2	When I face difficulties with bank web site, I like to refer to customer services for assistance.	
	RMP3	I am sure that I can solve problems during usage of banking	

		web site.	
	RMP4	I feel stressed when I cannot correct my mistake during transaction via bank web site.	
Integration Stage	INGT1	I am satisfied with the banking web site.	
	INGT2	Web site banking enables me to save effort.	
	INGT3	The services on bank web site are clear.	
	INGT4	I am interested in using bank web site services in the future.	

Table 3: Construct Items of all potential success factors.

Variable	Code	Adapted Statement	Source
Security	SEC1	Bank web site should clearly display security policies.	Sobihah et al., 2015
	SEC2	Bank web site should make it easy to contact customer representatives.	
	SEC3	Bank web site should provide financial confidentiality.	
	SEC4	Bank should focus on symbols that show the web site is secure.	
Privacy	PRI1	Bank web site executives should not misuse my personal information.	Sun et al., 2015; Sobihah et al., 2015
	PRI2	Bank should not give other web sites or third party access to my information.	
	PRI3	Bank web site should be really concerned with privacy of the users.	
	PRI4	Bank should make the customer feel safe when sending personal information to the web site.	
Customer support	CUS1	Bank web site should be keen to follow-up customer's requests.	Rahi et al., 2017
	CUS2	Bank web site should be keen to keep promises with customer's issues.	
	CUS3	Bank web site should display contact information (e-mail addresses, phone numbers).	
	CUS4	Bank web site staff should be a good problem solver.	
Accurate knowledge content	AKC1	Bank should ensure that the content on web site is accurate.	Ecer, 2014; Sun et al., 2015
	AKC2	Bank should ensure that the content on web site is clear in meaning.	
	AKC3	Bank should ensure that the content on web site is easy to understand.	
	AKC4	Bank should ensure that the content on web site is understandable for customer to use.	
Appropriate knowledge presentation	AKP1	Bank web site content should have free of ambiguous language	(Jovovic et al., 2016)
	AKP2	Bank web site content should be continually updated.	
	AKP3	Bank web site content should be simple for users.	
	AKP4	Bank web site content should have minimal download time.	
Web design layout	WDL1	Bank web site should present high quality colors.	Cebi, 2013
	WDL2	Bank web site should present readable font.	
	WDL3	Bank web site should have attractive design screen layout.	
	WDL4	Design layout for bank web site is important for me.	

3.4 Pilot Study

Before administering the questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted and the data pre-tested. 30 questionnaires had been distributed in University Sains Islam Malaysia. Pilot test defined as a small mini-trial of a proposed study that tests the instrument as well as obtain insights into the likely conditions of the intended study. DeVellis (2016) posited that a pilot study is an important stage in scale development.

The aim of a pilot study is to authenticate the measures adopted by instrument validity and accuracy and to obtain additional awareness regarding the behaviour of the data and prepare for any possible issues that might be experienced during the main analysis. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2010), instrument accuracy demonstrates cohesion and consistency with which the constructs are measured while instrument validity exhibits the extent to which a measure or an instrument authentically represents the idea being measured.

The pilot study was administered to the respondents of the university chosen for this research. Malhotra (2008) stated that the sample for a pilot test should be between 15 to 30 respondents. In light of this, the study analysed the results of a pilot test using 30 respondents.

3.5 Questionnaire Content and Validity

Questionnaire content and validity is defined as the extent to which an instrument represents the construct it seeks to measure (Creswell, 2012). Consequently, content validity involves ensuring that the question asked with respect to construct significantly covers the proposed intent of the construct being measured. Content validity is undertaken by a panel of experts who are asked to scrutinize the construct composition and item suitability (Hair et al., 2006; Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). In this study, the researcher conferred the questionnaire to a panel of 6 experts in divergent fields; Management Information Systems, Economics, Applied Linguistics, and (ICT) Management, Education (measurement and evaluation), Education (psychology and educational methodology), so as to disclose any confusing questions and to elicit suggestions founded on their experiences in the field.

The questionnaire was comprehensively critiqued to determine adequacy, comprehensibility, quality, clarity, comfort level, and appropriateness of the questions for the subject. The experts' comments and suggestions were considered and it was suggested deleting some items that will be more productive to ensuring that the respondents are able to concentrate on the questions and thereby provide valid and reliable replies. Furthermore, alternative

studies have suggested that the number of items in a scale has a consequence on responses, and that a shorter scale is an efficient means of decreasing response biases (Pather, 2008). Then, the amendments suggested by the experts were made, informed and agreed. This gave the researcher the opportunity to undertake amendments regarding the arrangement and words in some items, flow and sequencing of the questionnaire. The final questionnaire was ascertained to be understandable, succinct, designed well and valid to be used for the pilot study.

3.6 Reliability Tests

Reliability tests ascertain the level to which the items measure the same concept routinely in the construct. In other words, these tests measure the relationship between items in measuring the construct. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is a common utilized statistic for supposing internal consistency between items and demonstrates the typical inter-correlations of items measuring an idea. This research utilized Cronbach's alpha test to investigate the instrument reliability using SPSS Version 21. The threshold acceptable reliability is a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 and above, although 0.60 is deemed adequate for explanatory studies (Hair et al., 2010). Cronbach's alpha for all constructs utilized in this research was above the threshold. The value ranges from 0.791 to 0.910, thereby intimating that an acceptable internal consistency was attained. Table 4 below illustrates the summary of the reliability tests. Because all alpha values were 0.7 and above, the assumption was that all the constructs were adequately dependable, and items of each construct are constant among themselves in measuring each construct.

Table 4: Cronbach's alpha for the variables used in this research

Construct	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Dependent variable		
Knowledge transfer stages	16	0.863
Initiation	4	0.848
Implementation	4	0.810
Ramp-up	4	0.830
Integration	4	0.857
Independent variable		
Web site user	12	0.876
Security		0.923
Privacy		0.892
Customer support		0.904
Content	12	0.855
Accurate knowledge content		0.910
Appropriate knowledge presentation		0.901
Web site layout		0.791

The next step in this research is full research data collection, 800 questionnaires will distribute to eight public universities respondent in Malaysia. Before that, the determination of the probability sampling of respondents for the individual university is needed. The probability sampling calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Probability sampling of a respondents} = NP * NS / T$$

(NP= Number of population in each university, NS= Number of sample to be distributed, T= the total of the population at all universities).

4. Data Analysis Technique

Finally, exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and structural model take place on all variables to ascertain the relationships between all the variables. A summary description of the analysis is shown below. A descriptive analysis shows the key features of data in this research and provides summaries about the sample and measure with illustrated graphics which is discerned from deductive statistics.

Reliability analysis based on Cronbach alpha measures the internal consistency and the reliability of the items. Cronbach alpha reliability and validity test was carried out at 0.70 as the minimum level accepted. To reduce data to a smaller set of variables and to explore the underlying theoretical structure of the phenomena exploratory factor analysis used by SPSS; to uncover the underlying structure of a relatively large set of variables.

To examine scale accuracy of the potential success factors, confirmatory factor analysis using by AMOS (Dubihlela et al., 2014). To validate the research model, data analysis in this study was performed using structural modelling. This approach was chosen because of its ability to test causal relationships between constructs with multiple measurement items.

5. References

- [1]. Abdullah, A. R., Som, N. S. M., Ibrahim, A., & Sheriff, N. M. 2015. 'Internet Service Features and Satisfaction among Internet Banking Users'. *Journal of Management Research*. Vol. 7. No. 2. pp. 400. <http://doi.org/10.5296/jmr.v7i2.6944>
- [2]. Aghdasi, M., M. Bazrafshan, and M. Ranjbarfard. 2015. 'Identifying the Barriers of Knowledge Transfer in Collaborative Processes of Public Service Sector'. *Industrial Engineering and Operations Management (IEOM)*, 2015 International Conference On 1–11.
- [3]. Aquilani, B., Silvestri, C., Ruggieri, A., & Gatti, C. (2017). 2017. 'Article Information': 29:184–213.
- [4]. Azizan, Nurdiana, Ross Smith, and Vanessa Cooper. 2011. 'Critical Success Factors for Knowledge Transfer via Government Websites'. *Journal of E-Government Studies and Best Practices* 2011:1–12.
- [5]. binti Mohamad Sani, Nur Syafiqah and Noreen Izza binti Arshad. 2014. 'A Literature Review: Towards a Model to Measure the Impact of Knowledge Transfer with the Presence of IT Support'. *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Information Technology and Multimedia* (2010):206–11.
- [6]. Brady, Michael K., J. Joseph Jr. Cronin, Tim Brady, Michael K. Brady, and J. Joseph Jr. Cronin. 2001. 'Some New Thoughts on Conceptualizing Perceived Service Quality: A Hierarchical Approach'. *The American Aviation Experience* 65(3):34–49.
- [7]. Brar et al. 2015. 'E-banking Service Quality: A Study of Retail Customer 's Perspicacity'. No. 2000. pp. 182–193.
- [8]. Budiardjo, Eko K. and Eko K. Budiardjo. 2017. 'The Impact of Knowledge Management System Quality on the Usage Continuity and Recommendation Intention Ervi Cofriyanti Recommended Citation: The Impact of Knowledge Management System Quality on the Usage Continuity and Recommendation Intention Gilang Pam'. 9(2):200–224.
- [9]. Cader, Yoosuf, K. Kathleen O'neill, Ayesha Ali Blooshi, Amena Ali Bakheet Al Shouq, Barra Hussain Mohamed Fadaaq, and Farah Galal Ali. 2013. 'Knowledge Management in Islamic and Conventional Banks in the United Arab Emirates'. *Management Research Review* 36:388–99.
- [10]. Cebi, S. 2013. 'Determining importance degrees of website design parameters based on interactions and types of websites'. *Decision Support Systems*. Vol. 54. No. 2. pp. 1030–1043. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2012.10.036>
- [11]. Considine, E., & Cormican, K. 2016. 'Self-service Technology Adoption: An Analysis of Customer to Technology Interactions'. *Procedia Computer Science*. Vol. 100. pp. 103–109. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.09.129>
- [12]. Cooper, V., Lichtenstein, S., & Smith, R. 2007. 'Enabling Successful Web-based

- Information Technology Support for Enterprise Customers: A Service Provider Perspective of Stakeholder-based Issues Vanessa'. Vol. 9. No. 2. pp. 271–288. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemp>.
- [13]. Cooper, Vanessa A. 2009. 'A Review of the Critical Success Factor Method Using Insights from an Interpretive Case Study'. *Journal of Information Technology Case and Application Research* 11(3):9–42.
- [14]. Creswell, J. W. 2012. 'Steps in Conducting a Scholarly Mixed Methods Study'.
- [15]. Dayan, R., Heisig, P., & Matos, F. (2017). 'The Study and Practice of Leadership'. *Journal of Knowledge Management* 4(1):64–74.
- [16]. DeVellis, R. F. 2016. *Scale development: Theory and applications* (Vol. 26). Sage publications.
- [17]. Dickinger, Astrid and Brigitte Stangl. 2013. 'Website Performance and Behavioral Consequences: A Formative Measurement Approach'. *Journal of Business Research* 66(6):771–77.
- [18]. Dubihlela, J., & Molise - Khosa, P. 2014. 'Impact of e-CRM Implementation on Customer Loyalty, Customer Retention and Customer Profitability for Hoteliers along the Vaal Meander of South Africa'. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. Vol. 5. No. 16. pp. 175–183. <http://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n16p175>
- [19]. Ecer, F. 2014. 'A hybrid banking websites quality evaluation model using AHP and COPRAS-G: a Turkey case'. *Technological and Economic Development of Economy*. Vol. 20. No. 4. pp. 758–782. <http://doi.org/10.3846/20294913.2014.915596>
- [20]. Farzin, Mohammad Reza, Mohammad Safari Kahreh, Mostafa Hesani, and Ali Khalouei. 2014. 'A Survey of Critical Success Factors for Strategic Knowledge Management Implementation: Applications for Service Sector'. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 109:595–99.
- [21]. Ghasemaghaei, M., & Hassanein, K. 2016. 'A macro model of online information quality perceptions: A review and synthesis of the literature'. *Computers in Human Behavior*. Vol. 55. pp. 972–991. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.mineng.2015.11.007>
- [22]. Giannakopoulos, Georgios, Damianos P. Sakas, Dimitrios S. Vlachos, Daphne Kyriaki-Manessi, Nikos S. Kanellos, and Lefteris S. Papadimitriou. 2013. 'The Networking of High-Tech Firms as Basis for Knowledge Transfer'. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 73:263–67.
- [23]. Gooraki, E., & Shirazi, A. N. M. 2014. 'Defining qualitative assessing parameters of Iran banks website'. *Requirements Engineering*. Vol. 19. No. 1. pp. 81–87. <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00766-012-0160-5>
- [24]. Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B., Anderson, R., & Tatham, R. 2006. 'Multivariate Data Analysis' (6th ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- [25]. Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. 2010. 'Multivariate data analysis' (Vol. 6): Pearson Prentice Hall Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- [26]. Ilyas, Asad, Hammad Nasir, Muhammad Rizwan Malik, Usman Ejaz Mirza, Saleha Munir, and Ali Sajid. 2013. 'Assessing the Service Quality of Bank Using SERVQUAL Model'. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business* 4(11):390–400.
- [27]. Jovovic, Radislav, Elvis Lekic, and Miroslav Jovovic. 2016. 'Monitoring the Quality of Services in Electronic Banking'. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice* 5(3):99–119.
- [28]. Kulkarni, Chinmay C. and S. A. Kulkarni. 2013. 'Human Agent Knowledge Transfer Applied to Web Security'. *2013 4th International Conference on Computing, Communications and Networking Technologies, ICCCNT 2013* 4–7.
- [29]. Liang, Ping and Kebao Wu. 2010. 'Knowledge Management in Banks'. *Proceedings of the International Conference on E-Business and E-Government, ICEE 2010* 1819–22.
- [30]. Loiacono, Eleanor, Richard Watson, and Dale Goodhue. 2007. 'WebQual: An Instrument for Consumer Evaluation of Web Sites'. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce* 11(3):51–87.
- [31]. Lumbera, Wilbert D., Judy Ann G. Silva, Renzie Mae P, and Amabelle G. Viñas. 2019. 'Bricks or Clicks: A Banking Approach'. (2):217–30.

- [32]. Mahmadi, F. N., & Zaaba, Z. F. 2018. '709-716'. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 13(3):709–16.
- [33]. Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commissions. (2018). Internet users survey 2018. Retrieved from <https://www.skmm.gov.my/skmmgovmy/media/General/pdf/Internet-Users-Survey-2018.pdf>
- [34]. Malhotra, N.K. 2008. 'Essentials of marketing: An applied orientation' (2nd ed.). Australia: Pearson Education.
- [35]. Myers, M. D., and Avison, D. 2002. *Qualitative Research in Information Systems*, London: Sage Publications
- [36]. Nakanishi, Yoshinobu. 2014. 'Knowledge Transfer as Isomorphism: Diffusion of Administrative Innovation in the International Civil Aviation Domain'. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology* 5(3):175–82.
- [37]. Noor, Noorazah and Juhana Salim. 2011. 'Factors Influencing Employee Knowledge Sharing Capabilities in Electronic Government Agencies in Malaysia'. *International Journal of Computer Science Issues* 8(4):106–14.
- [38]. Nonaka, I. (1994). A dynamic theory of organizational knowledge creation. *Organization science*, 5(1), 14-37.
- [39]. Pak, Y. S., Ra, W., & Lee, J. M. (2015). An integrated multi-stage model of knowledge management in international joint ventures: Identifying a trigger for knowledge exploration and knowledge harvest. *Journal of world Business*, 50(1), 180-191.
- [40]. Paramsothy, Vijayan, Peter Woods, and Murali Raman. 2013. 'Success Factors for Implementation of Entrepreneurial Knowledge Management in Malaysian Banks'. *Journal of Information & Knowledge Management* 12(02):1350015.
- [41]. Pather, S. 2008. 'Using scale reduction techniques for improved quality of survey information'. Vol. 10. No. September. .
- [42]. Paulin, Dan and Kaj Suneson. 2012. 'Knowledge Transfer, Knowledge Sharing and Knowledge Barriers-Three Blurry Terms in KM Knowledge Transfer, Knowledge Sharing and Knowledge Barriers – Three Blurry Terms in KM'. (January).
- [43]. Rahi, Samar, Norjaya Mohd Yasin, and Feras Mi Alnaser. 2017. 'Measuring the Role of Website Design, Assurance, Customer Service and Brand Image Towards Customer Loyalty and Intention to Adopt Internet Banking'. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce* 21(S8):1–18.
- [44]. Randiwela, Pradeep. 2018. *Undergraduates Attitude towards Internet Banking: With Reference to SLIIT UNDERGRADUATES ATTITUDE TOWARDS USE OF INTERNET BANKING: WITH REFERENCE TO SLIIT*.
- [45]. Rodrigues, Luís Filipe, Carlos J. Costa, and Abílio Oliveira. 2017. 'How Does the Web Game Design Influence the Behavior of E-Banking Users?' *Computers in Human Behavior*.
- [46]. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2010. 'Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building'
- [47]. Sobihah, M., M. Mohamad, N. A. M. Ali, and W. Z. Wan Ismail. 2015. 'E-Commerce Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction, Belief and Loyalty: A Proposal'. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* 6(2):260–66.
- [48]. Sun, Jun, Ying Wang, Zhaojun Yang, and Yali Zhang. 2015. 'Rethinking E-Commerce Service Quality: Does Website Quality Still Suffice?' *Journal of Computer Information Systems* 55(4):62–72.
- [49]. Szulanski, G. 1996. 'Exploring internal stickiness: impediments to the transfer of best practice within the firm'. Vol. 17. pp. 27–43.
- [50]. Szulanski, G. 2000. 'THE PROCESS OF KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER: A DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF STICKINESS THE PROCESS OF KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER: A DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF STICKINESS'.
- [51]. Tan, C., Benbasat, I., & Cenfetelli, R. T. 2016. 'RESEARCH ARTICLE AN EXPLORATORY STUDY OF THE FORMATION AND IMPACT OF ELECTRONIC SERVICE FAILURES Summary of Extant Literature on Service Failure'. Vol. 40. No. 1. pp. 1–31.
- [52]. Torabi, Mir Hamid Reza, Abdulkarim Kyani, and Hussein Falakinia. 2016. 'An Investigation of the Impact of Knowledge Management on Human Resource Performance in Management of Keshavarzi Bank Branches in Tehran'. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 230(May):471–81.

- [53]. Usman, Ahmad Kabir. 2018. 'An Investigation into the Critical Success Factors for E-Banking Frauds Prevention in Nigeria By A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfilment for the Requirements for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the University of Central Lancashire October 2018'. (October).
- [54]. Vaca, Carlos Manosalvas, Maria Victoria Reyes, Luis Manosalvaas Vaca, and Lorena Paredes Andrade. 2018. 'Relationship of Leadership Styles and Tacit and Explicit Knowledge Sharing in Technology Companies'. *2017 Congreso Internacional de Innovacion y Tendencias En Ingenieria, CONIITI 2017 - Conference Proceedings 2018-Janua*:1-7.
- [55]. Yang, M., Chen, J. C. H., Wu, C., Chao, H., Jen, F., & City, X. 2010. 'On characteristics influencing consumer ' s intention to use web-based self-service'. Vol. 29. No. 510. pp. 41-49.
- <http://doi.org/10.3233/HSM-2010-0717>
- [56]. Zhou, R., Wang, X., Shi, Y., Zhang, R., Zhang, L., & Guo, H. (2018). Measuring e-service quality and its importance to customer satisfaction and loyalty: an empirical study in a telecom setting. *Electronic Commerce Research*, 1-23.
- [57]. Zhou, X., & Lin, Y. 2015. 'The Study on the Influence Mechanism of Website Features on Consumer Purchase Intention'. 2015 8th International Symposium on Computational Intelligence and Design (ISCID). pp. 104-107. <http://doi.org/10.1109/ISCID.2015.295>
- [58]. Zikmund, W. G., et al. 2010. 'Business Research Methods' (8th edition), South-Western Cengage, USA, 2010.
- [59]. Akinnuli, B. O. & Akintayo, T. C. (2019) Simulation of a Designed Portable Domestic Gas Baking Oven for its Fabrication Acceptability Prediction. *Journal of Global Scientific Research*. Vol. 1. pp122-134